

Fuzzy soft separation axioms in fuzzy soft topological spaces

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Abstract. Fuzzy soft separation axioms was introduced by Mahanta and Das ([5]) using the definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point' and 'the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft point', and 'distinct of fuzzy soft points' in there sense. In this paper we, introduce fuzzy soft separation axioms in terms of the modified definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point', the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft set' and 'distinct of fuzzy soft points'([7]). Also, we study some of their properties. Finally, we discuss fuzzy soft topological property for such spaces.

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1. Introduction

Prof. L. A. Zadeh[14] in 1965, introduced the concept of fuzzy set and fuzzy set operations.Chang [2] introduced the concept of fuzzy topology on a set X by axiomatizing a collection T of fuzzy subsets of X .

The concept of soft sets was first introduced by Molodtsov [8] in 1999 as a general mathematical tool for dealing with uncertain objects. Cagman et al. [1] and Shabir et al. [12] introduced soft topological spaceindependently in 2011. Maji et al. [6] introduced the concept of fuzzy soft set and some of its properties. Tanay et al. [13] introduced the definition of fuzzy soft topology over a subset of the initial universe set. Later, Roy and Samanta [11] gave the definition of fuzzy soft topology over the initial universe set. In [4], Kharal and Ahmed defined the notion of a mapping on classes of fuzzy soft sets.Mahanta and Das ([5]) introduced the fuzzy soft separation axioms $T_i(i = 0; 1; 2; 3; 4)$ by using the definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point' and 'the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft point ', and 'distinct of fuzzy soft points' in his sense.

In the present paper, we introduce fuzzy soft separation axioms $T_i(i = 0; 1; 2; 3; 4)$ in terms of the modified definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point', the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft set' and 'distinct of fuzzy soft points' ([7]) and we study some of their properties. Finally, we discuss some fuzzy soft topological property for such spaces.

2. Preliminaries

First we recall basic definitions and results.

Definition 2.1.([14]) Let X be a non-empty set. A fuzzy set A in X is defined by a membership function $\mu_A: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ whose value $\mu_A(x)$ represents the "grade of membership" of x in A for $x \in X$. The set of all fuzzy sets in a set X is denoted by I^X , where I is the closed unit interval $[0,1]$.

Definition 2.2. ([14]) If $A, B \in I^X$, then, we have:

- (1) $A \leq B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) \leq \mu_B(x), \forall x \in X;$
- (2) $A = B \Leftrightarrow \mu_A(x) = \mu_B(x), \forall x \in X;$
- (3) $C = A \vee B \Leftrightarrow \mu_C(x) = \max(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \forall x \in X;$
- (4) $D = A \wedge B \Leftrightarrow \mu_D(x) = \min(\mu_A(x), \mu_B(x)), \forall x \in X;$
- (5) $E = A^c \Leftrightarrow \mu_E(x) = 1 - \mu_A(x), \forall x \in X.$

Definition 2.3. ([8]) Let X be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Let $P(X)$ denotes the power set of X and $A \subseteq E$. A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over X if F is a mapping given by

$$F : A \rightarrow P(X).$$

In other words, a soft set is a parameterized family of subsets of the set X . For $e \in A$, $F(e)$ may be considered as the set of e -approximate elements of the soft set (F, A) .

Definition 2.4. ([11]) Let X be an initial universe set and E be a set of parameters. Let $A \subseteq E$. A fuzzy soft set f_A over X is a mapping from E to I^X , i.e., $f_A: E \rightarrow I^X$, where $f_A(e) \neq 0_X$ if $e \in A \subseteq E$, and $f_A(e) = 0_X$ if $e \notin A$, where 0_X denotes empty fuzzy set in X . The family of all fuzzy soft sets over X is denoted by $FSS(X, E)$.

Definition 2.5.([11]) The fuzzy soft set $f_A \in FSS(X, E)$. is called null fuzzy soft set, denoted by $\tilde{0}_E$, if for all $e \in A$, $f_A(e) = 0_X$.

Definition 2.6.([11]) Let $f_E \in FSS(X, E)$. The fuzzy soft set f_E is called absolute fuzzy soft set, denoted by $\tilde{1}_E$, if for all $e \in E$, $f_E(e) = 1_X$ where $1_X(x) = 1$ for all $x \in X$.

Definition 2.7.([11]) Let $f_A, g_B \in FSS(X, E)$. f_A is called a fuzzy soft subset of g_B if $A \subseteq B$ and $f_A(e) \leq g_B(e)$ for every $e \in E$ and we write $f_A \sqsubseteq g_B$. f_A and g_B are said to be equal, denoted by $f_A = g_B$ if $f_A \sqsubseteq g_B$ and $g_B \sqsubseteq f_A$.

Definition 2.8.([11]) Let $f_A, g_B \in FSS(X, E)$. The union (resp. intersection) of f_A and g_B is also a fuzzy soft set h_C , defined by $h_C(e) = f_A(e) \vee g_B(e)$ (resp. $h_C(e) = f_A(e) \wedge g_B(e)$) for all $e \in E$, where $C = A \cup B$ (resp. $C = A \cap B$). Here we write $h_C = f_A \sqcup g_B$ (resp. $h_C = f_A \sqcap g_B$).

Definition 2.9.([11]) Let $f_A \in FSS(X, E)$. The fuzzy soft complement of f_A , denoted by f_A^c , is a fuzzy soft set defined by $f_A^c(e) = 1_X - f_A(e)$ for every $e \in E$.

Clearly $(f_A^c)^c = f_A, (\tilde{1}_E)^c = \tilde{0}_E$ and $(\tilde{0}_E)^c = \tilde{1}_E$.

Definition 2.10.[11] Let \mathfrak{T} be a collection of fuzzy soft sets over a universe X with a fixed set of parameters E , then \mathfrak{T} is called a fuzzy soft topology on X if

- (1) $\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E \in \mathfrak{T}$,
- (2) The union of any members of \mathfrak{T} belongs to \mathfrak{T} ,
- (3) The intersection of any two members of \mathfrak{T} belongs to \mathfrak{T} .

The triple (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is called a fuzzy soft topological space over X . Also, each member of \mathfrak{T} is called a fuzzy soft open set in (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) and their fuzzy soft complements are called fuzzy soft closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) . The family of all fuzzy soft closed sets in (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is denoted by \mathfrak{T}^c

Definition. 2.12. [10] Let (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) be a fuzzy soft topological space and $f_A \in FSS(X, E)$. The fuzzy soft closure of f_A , denoted by $cl(f_A)$, is defined as $cl(f_A) = \cap \{h_C : h_C \in \mathfrak{T}^c, f_A \subseteq h_C\}$. Clearly, $cl(f_A)$ is the smallest fuzzy soft closed set over X which contains f_A .

Definition 2.13.[5,9] Let (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) be a fuzzy soft topological space and $Y \subseteq X$. Let h_E^Y be a fuzzy soft set over (Y, E) i.e., $h_E^Y: E \rightarrow I^Y$ such that

$$h_E^Y(e)(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in Y \\ 0 & \text{if } x \notin Y \end{cases}$$

Let $\mathfrak{T}_Y = \{h_E^Y \cap g_B : g_B \in \mathfrak{T}\}$, then \mathfrak{T}_Y is a fuzzy soft topology on (Y, E) called a fuzzy soft subspace topology for (Y, E) and (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is called a fuzzy soft subspace of (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) . If $h_E^Y \in \mathfrak{T}$ [resp. $h_E^Y \in \mathfrak{T}^c$] then (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is called fuzzy soft open [resp. closed] subspace of (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) .

Definition 2.13.[5] A fuzzy soft set g_A is said to be a fuzzy soft point, denoted by e_{g_A} , if for the element $e \in A$, $g_A(e) \neq 0_X$ and $g_A(e') = 0_X, \forall e' \in A - \{e\}$.

Definition 2.14.[5] The complement of a fuzzy soft point e_{g_A} is a fuzzy soft point $(e_{g_A})^c$ such that $g_A^c(e) = 1_X - g_A(e)$ and $g_A^c(e') = 0_X, \forall e' \in A - \{e\}$.

Definition 2.15.[5] A fuzzy soft point e_{g_A} is said to be a fuzzy soft set h_C , denoted by $e_{g_A} \in h_C$ if for the element $e \in C \cup A$, $g(e) \leq h(e)$.

Theorem 2.16.[5] A fuzzy soft point e_{g_A} satisfy the following properties.

- (1) If $e_{g_A} \tilde{\in} h_A$ then e_{g_A} may or may not belong to h_A^c ,
- (2) If $e_{g_A} \tilde{\in} h_A \not\Rightarrow (e_{g_A})^c \tilde{\in} h_A^c$,
- (3) The union of all the fuzzy soft points of a fuzzy soft set is equal to the fuzzy soft set.

Definition 2.17.[7] A fuzzy soft point e_{x_α} over X is a fuzzy soft set over X defined as follows:

$$e_{x_\alpha}(e') = \begin{cases} x_\alpha & \text{if } e' = e \\ 0_X & \text{if } e' \in E - \{e\}, \end{cases}$$

where x_α is the fuzzy point ([11]) in X with support x and value $\alpha, \alpha \in (0, 1)$.

A fuzzy soft point e_{x_α} is said to belong to a fuzzy soft set f_A , denoted by $e_{x_\alpha} \tilde{\in} f_A$ if $\alpha < f_A(e)(x)$. Two fuzzy soft points e_{x_α} and e'_{y_β} are said to be distinct if $x \neq y$ or $e \neq e'$.

Definition 2.18. ([4]) Let $FSS(X, E)$ and $FSS(Y, K)$ be the families of all fuzzy soft sets over X and Y , respectively. Let $u : X \rightarrow Y$ and $p : E \rightarrow K$ be two mappings. Then a fuzzy soft mapping $f_{up} : FSS(X, E) \rightarrow FSS(Y, K)$ is defined as follows: for a fuzzy soft set $f_A \in FSS(X, E)$, $\forall k \in p(E) \subseteq K$ and $y \in Y$, we have

$$f_{up}(f_A)(k)(y) = \begin{cases} \bigvee_{x \in u^{-1}(y)} \bigvee_{e \in p^{-1}(k) \cap A} f_A(e)(x) & \text{if } u^{-1}(y) \neq \emptyset, p^{-1}(k) \cap A \neq \emptyset, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

$f_{up}(f_A)$ is called the fuzzy soft image of a fuzzy soft set f_A .

Definition 2.19. ([4]) Let $u : X \rightarrow Y$ and $p : E \rightarrow K$ be two mappings.

Let $f_{up} : FSS(X, E) \rightarrow FSS(Y, K)$ be fuzzy soft mapping and $g_B \in FSS(Y, K)$. Then $f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)$, is a fuzzy soft set in $FSS(X, E)$, defined by

$$f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)(e)(x) = g_B(p(e))(u(x)), \quad \forall e \in E, x \in X.$$

$f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)$ is called the fuzzy soft inverse image of g_B .

If u and p are injective then the fuzzy soft mapping f_{up} is said to be fuzzy soft injective. If u and p are surjective then the fuzzy soft mapping f_{up} is said to be fuzzy soft surjective. The fuzzy soft mapping f_{up} is called fuzzy soft constant, if u and p are constant. f_{up} is said to be fuzzy soft bijective if f_{up} is fuzzy soft injective and fuzzy soft surjective mapping.

Definition 2.20. ([10]) Let (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, E) and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2, K) be two fuzzy soft topological spaces and $f_{up} : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, E) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2, K)$ be a fuzzy soft mapping. Then f_{up} is called

- (1) fuzzy soft continuous if $f_{up}^{-1}(g_E) \in \mathfrak{T}_1$, for all $g_E \in \mathfrak{T}_2$,
- (2) fuzzy soft open if $f_{up}(f_E) \in \mathfrak{T}_2$, for all $f_E \in \mathfrak{T}_1$.
- (3) fuzzy soft homeomorphism if f_{up} is fuzzy soft bijective, fuzzy soft continuous and fuzzy soft open.

Theorem 2.21. ([10]) Let (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, E) and (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2, K) be two fuzzy soft topological spaces and $f_{up} : (X, \mathfrak{T}_1, E) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2, K)$ be a fuzzy soft mapping. Then the following are equivalent:

- (1) f_{up} is fuzzy soft continuous,
- (2) $f_{up}^{-1}(g_E) \in \mathfrak{T}_1^c$ for each $g_E \in \mathfrak{T}_2^c$.

Proposition 2.22. ([4]) Let $FSS(X, E)$ and $FSS(Y, K)$ be two families of fuzzy soft sets. For the fuzzy soft mapping $f_{up} : FSS(X, E) \rightarrow FSS(Y, K)$, the following statements hold,

- (1) $f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)^c = (f_{up}^{-1}(g_B))^c \forall g_B \in FSS(Y, K)$.
- (2) $f_{up}(f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)) \subseteq g_B \forall g_B \in FSS(Y, K)$. If f_{up} is fuzzy soft surjective, the equality hold.
- (3) $f_A \subseteq f_{up}^{-1}(f_{up}(f_A)) \forall f_A \in FSS(X, E)$. If f_{up} is fuzzy soft injective, the equality hold.
- (4) $f_{up}(\tilde{0}_E) = \tilde{0}_K, f_{up}(\tilde{1}_E) \subseteq \tilde{1}_K$. If f_{up} is fuzzy soft injective, the equality hold.
- (5) $f_{up}^{-1}(\tilde{1}_K) = \tilde{1}_E$ and $f_{up}^{-1}(\tilde{0}_K) = \tilde{0}_E$.

- (6) If $f_A \sqsubseteq g_B$, then $f_{up}(f_A) \sqsubseteq f_{up}(g_B) \forall f_A, g_B \in FSS(X, E)$.
 (7) If $f_A \sqsubseteq g_B$. Then $f_{up}^{-1}(f_A) \sqsubseteq f_{up}^{-1}(g_B) \forall f_A, g_B \in FSS(Y, K)$.
 (8) $f_{up}^{-1}(\sqcup_{i \in J} (g_B)_i) = \sqcup_{i \in J} f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)_i$ and $f_{up}^{-1}(\prod_{i \in J} (g_B)_i) = \prod_{i \in J} f_{up}^{-1}(g_B)_i \forall (g_B)_i \in FSS(Y, K)$.
 (9) $f_{up}(\sqcup_{i \in J} (f_A)_i) = \sqcup_{i \in J} f_{up}(f_A)_i$ and $f_{up}(\prod_{i \in J} (f_A)_i) = \prod_{i \in J} f_{up}(f_A)_i \forall (f_A)_i \in FSS(X, E)$.
 If f_{up} is fuzzy soft injective, the equality hold.

3. Fuzzy soft separation axioms

Mahanta and Das ([5]) had introduced the concepts fuzzy soft T_0 -spaces and fuzzy soft T_1 -spaces using the definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point' and 'the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft point', in his sense. Here we define fuzzy soft T_0 -space and fuzzy soft T_1 -space in terms of the modified definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point', 'the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft set' and 'distinct of fuzzy soft points' in Definition 2.17.

Remark 3.1. Instead of the notation e_{x_α} in Definition 2.17, we shall use the notation (e, x_α) . Therefore, the fuzzy soft points (e, x_α) and (\acute{e}, y_β) are said to be distinct in (X, E) if $e \neq \acute{e}$ or $x \neq y$.

The proof of the following theorem follows directly from definition of fuzzy softpoint and therefore omitted.

Theorem 3.2. A fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) satisfying the following properties:

- (1) If $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_A$ then (e, x_α) may or may not belongs to f_A^c ,
- (2) If $(e, x_\alpha) \sqcap f_A = \tilde{0}_\theta$ then $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\notin} f_A$ and $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_A^c$,
- (3) If $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_A$ and $\alpha > 0.5$, then $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\notin} f_A^c$,
- (4) If $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_A \Rightarrow (e, x_\alpha)^c \tilde{\in} f_A^c$,
- (5) The union of all fuzzy soft points of a fuzzy softset is equal to the fuzzy soft set.

Definition 3.3. A fuzzy soft topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is said to be a fuzzy soft T_0 –space if forevery pair of distinct fuzzy soft points $(e, x_\alpha), (\acute{e}, y_\beta)$ there exists a fuzzy softopen set containing one of the points but not the other.

Example 3.4. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and

$\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, (f_E)_1, (f_E)_2, (f_E)_3, (f_E)_4, (f_E)_5, (f_E)_6\}$ where

$$(f_E)_1 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_2 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_3 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_4 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_5 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_6 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

Then, clearly \mathfrak{T} is a fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) . Also for every pair of distinct fuzzy soft points there exists fuzzy soft open set containing one of the points but not the other. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_0 -space.

Example 3.5. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E, g_E\}$ where

$$f_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, g_E = \left\{ \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

Then \mathfrak{T} is a fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) but (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is not a fuzzy soft T_0 –space.

Example 3.6. The discrete fuzzy soft topological space is a fuzzy soft T_0 –space, but the indiscrete fuzzy soft topological space is not fuzzy soft T_0 .

Theorem 3.7. A fuzzy soft subspace (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) of a fuzzy soft T_0 -space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_0 .

Proof. Let $(e, x_\alpha), (\acute{e}, y_\beta)$ betwodistinct fuzzy soft points in (Y, E) . Then these fuzzy soft points are also in (X, E) . Hence, there exists a fuzzy softopen set f_E in \mathfrak{T} containing one of the points say, (e, x_α) , but not (\acute{e}, y_β) . Thus, $h_E^Y \sqcap f_E$ is a fuzzy softopen set in (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) containing (e, x_α) but not (\acute{e}, y_β) . Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is fuzzy soft T_0 .

Definition 3.8. A fuzzy soft topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is said to be a fuzzy soft T_1 –space if for every pair of distinct fuzzy soft points $(e, x_\alpha), (\acute{e}, y_\beta)$ there exist fuzzy softopen sets f_E and g_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E, (\acute{e}, y_\beta) \tilde{\notin} f_E$ and $(\acute{e}, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} g_E, (e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\notin} g_E$.

Example 3.9. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and

$$\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, (f_E)_1, (f_E)_2, (f_E)_3, (f_E)_4, (f_E)_5, (f_E)_6, (f_E)_7, (f_E)_8, (f_E)_9, (f_E)_{10}, (f_E)_{11}, (f_E)_{12}\} \text{ where}$$

$$(f_E)_1 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_2 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_3 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_4 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_5 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_6 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_7 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_8 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_9 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_{10} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_{11} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_{12} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_1 –space.

Example 3.10. The discrete fuzzy soft topological space is a fuzzy soft T_1 –space, but the indiscrete fuzzy soft topological space is not fuzzy soft T_1 .

Theorem 3.11. A fuzzy soft subspace (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) of a fuzzy soft T_1 –space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_1 .

Proof. It is similar to the proof of Theorem 3.7.

Theorem 3.12. If every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) of a fuzzy soft topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft closed such that $\alpha > 0.5$, then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_1 .

Proof. Suppose that (e^1, x_α) and (e^2, y_β) two distinct fuzzy soft points in (X, E) . By hypothesis, (e^1, x_α) and (e^2, y_β) are fuzzy soft closed sets and $\alpha > 0.5, \beta > 0.5$. Hence, $(e^1, x_\alpha)^c$ and $(e^2, y_\beta)^c$ are fuzzy soft open sets where $(e^1, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} (e^2, y_\beta)^c$, $(e^2, y_\beta) \tilde{\notin} (e^2, y_\beta)^c$ and $(e^1, x_\alpha) \tilde{\notin} (e^1, x_\alpha)^c$, $(e^2, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} (e^1, x_\alpha)^c$. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_1 .

The condition $\alpha > 0.5$ in theorem 3.12, is necessary as shown by the following examples:

Example 3.13. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1\}$. Consider the collection \mathfrak{T} of fuzzy soft sets over $(X, E), \mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E, g_E, h_E\}$ where f_E, g_E and h_E are as follows:

$$f_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1-\alpha}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, g_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1-\beta} \right\} \right) \right\}, h_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1-\alpha}, \frac{x^2}{1-\beta} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

Then \mathfrak{T} is fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) and $(e^1, x_\alpha^1), (e^1, x_\beta^2)$ are two distinct fuzzy soft points in (X, E) such that for any fuzzy soft open set which containing (e^1, x_α^1) also containing (e^1, x_β^2) . Hence, (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is not fuzzy soft T_1 .

Remark 3.14. If (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_1 –space, then (e, x_α) maybe not a fuzzy soft closed set as the following example shows.

Example 3.15. In Example 3.9 (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_1 –space, but (e^1, x_α) is not fuzzy soft closed set. To show this, let $(e^1, x_\alpha^1) = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{\alpha} \right\} \right) \right\}$.

Then $(e^1, x_\alpha^1)^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1-\alpha}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}$ is not fuzzy soft open set i.e., (e^1, x_α^1) is not fuzzy soft closed set.

Definition 3.16. ([7]) A fuzzy soft topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is said to be a fuzzy soft T_2 -space if for every pair of distinct fuzzy soft points $(e, x_\alpha), (e', y_\beta)$ there exists disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $(e', y_\beta) \in g_E$.

Example 3.17. ([7]) Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and

$$\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, (f_E)_1, (f_E)_2, (f_E)_3, (f_E)_4, (f_E)_5, (f_E)_6, (f_E)_7, (f_E)_8, (f_E)_9, (f_E)_{10}, (f_E)_{11}, (f_E)_{12}, (f_E)_{13}, (f_E)_{14}\} \text{ where}$$

$$(f_E)_1 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_2 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_3 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_4 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_5 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_6 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_7 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_8 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_9 = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_{10} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_{11} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_{12} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\},$$

$$(f_E)_{13} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{0} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, (f_E)_{14} = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right), \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{0}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

Then, clearly \mathfrak{T} is fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) . Also, for every pair of distinct fuzzysoft points, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets in (X, E) containing them. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_2 -space.

Example 3.18. The discrete fuzzy soft topological space is a fuzzy soft T_2 -space, but the indiscrete fuzzy soft topological space is not a fuzzy soft T_2 .

Theorem 3.19. A fuzzy soft subspace (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) of fuzzy soft T_2 -space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_2 .

Proof. Let $(e, x_\alpha), (e', y_\beta)$ be two distinct fuzzy soft points in (Y, E) . Then, these fuzzy soft points are also in (X, E) . Hence, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E in \mathfrak{T} such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $(e', y_\beta) \tilde{\in} g_E$. Thus, $h_E^Y \cap f_E$ and $h_E^Y \cap g_E$ are disjoint fuzzy soft open sets in \mathfrak{T}_Y such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} h_E^Y \cap f_E$ and $(e', y_\beta) \tilde{\in} h_E^Y \cap g_E$. So, (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is a fuzzy soft T_2 -space.

Remark 3.20. From definitions one deduce the following implication hold:

$$\text{fuzzy soft } T_2 \implies \text{fuzzy soft } T_1 \implies \text{fuzzy soft } T_0$$

The inverse implications may not be true as shows is by the following examples.

Example 3.21. In Example 3.4, (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_0 -space but not fuzzy soft T_1 -space. Since $(e^1, x_\beta^2), (e^2, x_\alpha^1)$ are distinct fuzzy soft points and the only fuzzy soft open set which containing (e^1, x_β^2) is $\tilde{1}_E$ also containing (e^2, x_α^1) . Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is not fuzzy soft T_1 .

In Example 3.9, (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_1 -space but not fuzzy soft T_2 -space. Since $(e^1, x_\alpha^1), (e^2, x_\beta^2)$ are distinct fuzzy soft points and the only fuzzy soft open sets which containing $(e^1, x_\alpha^1), (e^2, x_\beta^2)$ are $(f_E)_1, (f_E)_2$ but they are not disjoint. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is not fuzzy soft T_2 .

Definition 3.22. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) be a fuzzy soft topological space. If for every fuzzy soft closed set h_E and every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \cap k_E = \tilde{0}_E$ there exists disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $k_E \sqsubseteq g_E$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is called fuzzy soft regular space.

Definition 3.23. A fuzzy soft topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is called a fuzzy soft T_3 -space if it is fuzzy soft T_1 and fuzzy soft regular.

Example 3.24. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E, g_E\}$ where

$$f_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, g_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

Then \mathfrak{T} is fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) . Now, $\mathfrak{T}^c = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E^c, g_E^c\}$ where

$$f_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, g_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

For the fuzzy soft point $(e^1, x_\alpha^1) \sqcap f_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$ there exist fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E such that $(e^1, x_\alpha^1) \tilde{\in} f_E, f_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E$ and $f_E \sqcap g_E = \tilde{0}_E$.

For the fuzzy soft point $(e^1, x_\beta^2) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$ there exist fuzzy soft open sets g_E and f_E such that $(e^1, x_\beta^2) \tilde{\in} g_E, g_E^c \sqsubseteq f_E$ and $g_E \sqcap f_E = \tilde{0}_E$.

Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_3 -space.

Example 3.25. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E, g_E\}$ where

$$f_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\}, 1 \right) \right\}, g_E = \left\{ \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\}, 1 \right) \right\}.$$

Then \mathfrak{T} is a fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) . Now, $\mathfrak{T}^c = \{\tilde{0}_E, \tilde{1}_E, f_E^c, g_E^c\}$ where

$$f_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^2 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}, g_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \left\{ \frac{x^1}{1}, \frac{x^2}{1} \right\} \right) \right\}.$$

By used fuzzy soft regularity on fuzzy soft closed sets as follows:

$$(e^1, x_\alpha^1) \sqcap f_E^c = \tilde{0}_E \implies \exists g_E^c, g_E \in \mathfrak{T} \text{ such that } (e^1, x_\alpha^1) \tilde{\in} g_E^c, f_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E \text{ and } g_E^c \sqcap g_E = \tilde{0}_E,$$

$$(e^1, x_\beta^2) \sqcap f_E^c = \tilde{0}_E \implies \exists g_E^c, g_E \in \mathfrak{T} \text{ such that } (e^1, x_\beta^2) \tilde{\in} g_E^c, f_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E \text{ and } g_E^c \sqcap g_E = \tilde{0}_E,$$

$$(e^2, x_{\alpha'}^1) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E \implies \exists f_E^c, f_E \in \mathfrak{T} \text{ such that } (e^2, x_{\alpha'}^1) \tilde{\in} f_E^c, g_E^c \sqsubseteq f_E \text{ and } f_E^c \sqcap f_E = \tilde{0}_E,$$

$$(e^2, x_{\beta'}^2) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E \implies \exists f_E^c, f_E \in \mathfrak{T} \text{ such that } (e^2, x_{\beta'}^2) \tilde{\in} f_E^c, g_E^c \sqsubseteq f_E \text{ and } f_E^c \sqcap f_E = \tilde{0}_E.$$

Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space, but not a fuzzy soft T_1 -space and hence not fuzzy soft T_3 .

Proposition 3.26. If (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space, then for any fuzzy soft open set g_E and a fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) in (X, E) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$, then there exists a fuzzy soft open set s_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} s_E \sqsubseteq cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq g_E$.

Proof. Suppose that (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space. Let g_E be a fuzzy soft open set in (X, E) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$. Now g_E^c is fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \sqcap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$ and (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft regular, therefore there exist two disjoint fuzzy soft open sets s_E and w_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \in s_E$ and $g_E^c \sqsubseteq w_E$. Now, w_E^c is a fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) such that $s_E \sqsubseteq w_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E$. Thus, $(e, x_\alpha) \in s_E \sqsubseteq cl(s_E)$ and $s_E \sqsubseteq w_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E$ and hence, $cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq g_E$. This proves that $(e, x_\alpha) \in s_E \sqsubseteq cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq g_E$.

Theorem 3.27. Every fuzzy soft regular space, in which every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) is fuzzy soft closed, is a fuzzy soft T_2 -space.

Proof. Let $(e, x_\alpha), (e', y_\beta)$ be two distinct fuzzy soft points of a fuzzy soft regular space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) . By hypothesis, (e', y_β) is fuzzy soft closed set and $(e, x_\alpha) \sqcap (e', y_\beta) = \tilde{0}_E$. From the fuzzy soft regularity, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E such that

$(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $(e, y_\beta) \sqsubseteq g_E$. Thus, $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $(e, y_\beta) \sqsubseteq g_E$. Thus $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$ and $(e, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} g_E$. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft T_2 –space.

Corollary 3.28. Every fuzzy soft T_3 –space, in which every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) is fuzzy soft closed is a fuzzy soft T_2 .

Theorem 3.29. A fuzzy soft subspace (Y, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) of a fuzzy soft T_3 –space (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft T_3 .

Proof. By Theorem 3.11, (Y, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is a fuzzy soft T_1 –space. Now, we want to prove that (X, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space. Let k_E be a fuzzy soft closed set in (Y, E) and (e, y_β) be a fuzzy soft point in (Y, E) such that $(e, y_\beta) \cap k_E = \tilde{0}_E$. Then, $k_E = h_E^Y \cap f_E$ (Theorem 4.9, [5]) for some fuzzy soft closed set f_E in (X, E) . Hence, $(e, y_\beta) \cap (h_E^Y \cap f_E) = \tilde{0}_E$. But $(e, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} h_E^Y$, so $(e, y_\beta) \cap f_E = \tilde{0}_E$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is fuzzy soft regular. Then, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets s_E and w_E in \mathfrak{T} such that $(e, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} s_E$ and $f_E \sqsubseteq w_E$. It follows that $h_E^Y \cap s_E$ and $h_E^Y \cap w_E$ are disjoint fuzzy soft open sets in \mathfrak{T}_Y such that $(e, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} h_E^Y \cap s_E$ and $k_E \sqsubseteq h_E^Y \cap w_E$. Therefore, (Y, \mathfrak{T}_Y, E) is fuzzy soft regular and thus fuzzy soft T_3 .

Definition 3.30. Let (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) be a fuzzy soft topological space. If for every disjoint fuzzy soft closed h_E, k_E there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets s_E and w_E such that $h_E \sqsubseteq s_E, k_E \sqsubseteq w_E$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is called fuzzy soft normal space. (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is called a fuzzy soft T_4 –space if it is fuzzy soft normal and fuzzy soft T_1 –space.

Example 3.31. Let $X = \{x^1, x^2\}, E = \{e^1, e^2\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E, g_E, h_E, k_E\}$ where
 $f_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}, g_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\},$
 $h_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}, k_E = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}.$
 Then \mathfrak{T} is fuzzy soft topology over (X, E) . Now, let $\mathfrak{T}^c = \{\tilde{1}_E, \tilde{0}_E, f_E^c, g_E^c, h_E^c, k_E^c\}$ where
 $f_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}, g_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\},$
 $h_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 1 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}, k_E^c = \left\{ \left(e^1 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 0 \end{Bmatrix} \right), \left(e^2 = \begin{Bmatrix} x^1 & x^2 \\ 0 & 1 \end{Bmatrix} \right) \right\}.$
 For the two disjoint fuzzy soft closed sets g_E^c and h_E^c there exists $g_E, h_E \in \mathfrak{T}$ such that $h_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E, g_E^c \sqsubseteq h_E$ and $g_E \cap h_E = \tilde{0}_E$.
 For the two disjoint fuzzy soft closed sets g_E^c and k_E^c there exists $h_E, g_E \in \mathfrak{T}$ such that $g_E^c \sqsubseteq h_E, k_E^c \sqsubseteq g_E$ and $h_E \cap g_E = \tilde{0}_E$.
 Then (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft normal space, but not a T_1 –space and hence not T_4 .

Proposition 3.32. If (X, \mathfrak{T}, E) is a fuzzy soft normal space, then for each fuzzy soft closed set k_E in (X, E) and any fuzzy soft open set g_E in (X, E) such that $k_E \cap g_E = \tilde{0}_E$ then there exists a fuzzy soft open set s_E such that $k_E \sqsubseteq s_E \sqsubseteq cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq g_E$.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) be a fuzzy soft normal space. Let k_E be a fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) and g_E be a fuzzy soft open set in (X, E) such that $k_E \cap g_E^c = \tilde{0}_E$, then $k_E \sqsubseteq g_E$. Now, k_E and g_E^c are two disjoint fuzzy soft closed sets in (X, E) . Since (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) is a fuzzy soft normal, so there exist two disjoint fuzzy soft open sets s_E and w_E such that $k_E \sqsubseteq s_E$, $g_E^c \sqsubseteq w_E$ and $s_E \cap w_E = \tilde{0}_E$, we have $s_E \sqsubseteq w_E^c$, but w_E^c is a fuzzy soft closed set and hence $cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq w_E^c$. Thus, we have $k_E \sqsubseteq s_E \sqsubseteq cl(s_E) \sqsubseteq g_E$.

Theorem 3.33. A fuzzy soft closed subspace (Y, \mathfrak{X}_Y, E) of a fuzzy soft normal space (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) is fuzzy soft normal.

Proof. Let $(k_E)_1$ and $(k_E)_2$ be disjoint fuzzy soft closed sets in (Y, E) . Then, $(k_E)_1 = h_E^Y \cap (f_E)_1$ and $(k_E)_2 = h_E^Y \cap (f_E)_2$ (Theorem 4.9 in [5]) for some fuzzy soft closed sets $(f_E)_1, (f_E)_2$ in (X, E) . Since h_E^Y is fuzzy soft closed in (X, E) , then $(k_E)_1, (k_E)_2$ are disjoint fuzzy soft closed sets in (X, E) . Since (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) is fuzzy soft normal, then there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets $(g_E)_1$ and $(g_E)_2$ in (X, E) such that $(k_E)_1 \sqsubseteq (g_E)_1$, $(k_E)_2 \sqsubseteq (g_E)_2$, and then, $(k_E)_1 \sqsubseteq (s_E)_1 = h_E^Y \cap (g_E)_1$, $(k_E)_2 \sqsubseteq (s_E)_2 = h_E^Y \cap (g_E)_2$. From definition of \mathfrak{X}_Y , we have $(s_E)_1, (s_E)_2 \in \mathfrak{X}_Y$ are fuzzy soft open sets in (Y, E) and $(s_E)_1 \cap (s_E)_2 = [h_E^Y \cap (g_E)_1] \cap [h_E^Y \cap (g_E)_2] = h_E^Y \cap [(g_E)_1 \cap (g_E)_2] = h_E^Y \cap \tilde{0}_E = \tilde{0}_E$. Therefore, (Y, \mathfrak{X}_Y, E) is fuzzy soft normal.

Theorem 3.34. Every fuzzy soft normal space, in which every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) is fuzzy soft closed, is a fuzzy soft regular space.

Proof. Let (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) be a fuzzy soft normal space and (e, x_α) be a fuzzy soft point and k_E be a fuzzy soft closed set such that $(e, x_\alpha) \cap k_E = \tilde{0}_E$. Since (e, x_α) is a fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) , then there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets s_E and w_E such that $(e, x_\alpha) \sqsubseteq s_E$, $k_E \sqsubseteq w_E$ and thus, $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\sqsubseteq} s_E$, $k_E \sqsubseteq w_E$. Therefore, (X, \mathfrak{X}, E) is fuzzy soft regular.

Corollary 3.35. Every fuzzy soft T_4 -space, in which every fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) is fuzzy soft closed, is a fuzzy soft T_3 .

Theorem 3.36. Let $f_{up}: (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K)$ be a fuzzy soft bijective and fuzzy soft open mapping. If (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) is a fuzzy soft T_i -space, then (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K) is a fuzzy soft T_i -space, $i = 0; 1; 2$

Proof. We prove the theorem for $(i = 2)$, for example, the other cases are similar. Let (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) be a fuzzy soft T_2 -space and $f_{up}: (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K)$ be a fuzzy soft bijective fuzzy soft open mapping, we want to show that (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K) is a fuzzy soft T_2 -space. So, let $(\acute{e}, x_\alpha), (\acute{s}, y_\beta)$ be two distinct fuzzy soft points in (Y, K) . Since f_{up} is

bijection mapping, then there exist two distinct fuzzy soft points $(e, a_\alpha), (s, b_\beta)$ in (X, E) such that $f_{up}(e, a_\alpha) = (\acute{e}, x_\alpha)$, $f_{up}(s, b_\beta) = (\acute{s}, y_\beta)$. But (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) is a fuzzy soft T_2 –space, so, there exists disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E in (X, E) such that $(e, a_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$, $(s, b_\beta) \tilde{\in} g_E$.

It follows that, $f_{up}(e, a_\alpha) = (\acute{e}, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(f_E)$, $f_{up}(s, b_\beta) = (\acute{s}, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(g_E)$ and $f_{up}(f_E) \cap f_{up}(g_E) = f_{up}(f_E \cap g_E) = f_{up}(\tilde{0}_E) = \tilde{0}_K$ (from Proposition 2.22).

Since $f_E, g_E \in \mathfrak{X}_1$, and f_{up} is a fuzzy soft open mapping, $f_{up}(f_E), f_{up}(g_E) \in \mathfrak{X}_2$. Now, there exists disjoint fuzzy soft open sets $f_{up}(f_E)$ and $f_{up}(g_E)$ in (Y, K) such that $(\acute{e}, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(f_E)$ and $(\acute{s}, y_\beta) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(g_E)$. Hence, (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K) is a fuzzy soft T_2 –space.

Definition 3.37. The property P is called a fuzzy soft topological property if it is preserved under a fuzzy soft homeomorphism mapping.

Corollary 3.38. The property of being fuzzy soft T_i –space ($i = 0; 1; 2$) is a fuzzy soft topological property.

Theorem 3.39. The property of being fuzzy soft T_i –space ($i = 3; 4$) is a fuzzy soft topological property.

Proof. We prove the theorem for ($i = 3$, for example), the other cases are similar.

Since, the property of being fuzzy soft T_1 –space is a fuzzy soft topological property, we only show that the property of fuzzy soft regularity is a fuzzy soft topological property.

Let $f_{up}: (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) \rightarrow (Y, \mathfrak{X}_2, K)$ be a fuzzy soft homeomorphism and (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space. Let k_E be a fuzzy soft closed set in (Y, K) and let (\acute{e}, y_α) be a fuzzy soft point in (Y, K) such that $(\acute{e}, y_\alpha) \cap k_E = \tilde{0}_K$. Since f_{up} is fuzzy soft surjective, there exists a fuzzy soft point (e, x_α) in (X, E) such that $f_{up}(e, x_\alpha) = (\acute{e}, y_\alpha)$. Since f_{up} is fuzzy soft continuous and k_E fuzzy soft closed in (Y, K) , we have $f_{up}^{-1}(k_E)$ a fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) from Theorem 2.21. Now, $f_{up}(e, x_\alpha) = (\acute{e}, y_\alpha)$, implies that $(e, x_\alpha) = f_{up}^{-1}(\acute{e}, y_\alpha)$ [as f_{up} is fuzzy soft injective] and since $(\acute{e}, y_\alpha) \cap k_E = \tilde{0}_K$, which implies that $f_{up}^{-1}((\acute{e}, y_\alpha) \cap k_E) = f_{up}^{-1}(\tilde{0}_K) = \tilde{0}_E$. Then $(e, x_\alpha) \cap f_{up}^{-1}(k_E) = \tilde{0}_E$. Now, $f_{up}^{-1}(k_E)$ is fuzzy soft closed set in (X, E) and (e, x_α) is a fuzzy soft point in (X, E) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \cap f_{up}^{-1}(k_E) = \tilde{0}_E$. But (X, \mathfrak{X}_1, E) is a fuzzy soft regular space, so, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets f_E and g_E in (X, E) such that $(e, x_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_E$, $f_{up}^{-1}(k_E) \subseteq g_E$ and therefore,

$f_{up}(e, x_\alpha) = (e, y_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(f_E)$, $f_{up}(f_{up}^{-1}(k_E)) = k_E \sqsubseteq f_{up}(g_E)$ [as f_{up} is fuzzy soft surjective] and $f_{up}(f_E) \cap f_{up}(g_E) = f_{up}(f_E \cap g_E) = f_{up}(\tilde{0}_E) = \tilde{0}_K$ [from Proposition 2.22]. Since f_{up} is a fuzzy soft open mapping, then $f_{up}(f_E), f_{up}(g_E) \in \mathfrak{T}_2$. Now, there exist disjoint fuzzy soft open sets $f_{up}(f_E)$ and $f_{up}(g_E)$ in (Y, K) such that $(e, y_\alpha) \tilde{\in} f_{up}(f_E)$ and $k_E \sqsubseteq f_{up}(g_E)$. Thus, (Y, \mathfrak{T}_2, K) is a fuzzy soft regular space.

4. Conclusion

In the present work, we introduce fuzzy soft separation axioms $T_i (i = 0; 1; 2; 3; 4)$ in terms of the modified definitions of a 'fuzzy soft point', the complement of a fuzzy soft point is a fuzzy soft set' and presented fundamentals properties such as fuzzy soft hereditary, fuzzy soft topological property. For future works, we consider to study on fuzzy soft separation axioms $T_i (i = 0; 1; 2; 3; 4)$ in generalized fuzzy soft topological spaces.

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